

ISSN 0066 4774

Antichthon

Volume Thirty-Seven 2003

JOURNAL OF THE AUSTRALASIAN SOCIETY FOR CLASSICAL STUDIES

Procne, Philomela, Tereus in Ovid's *Metamorphoses*:
A Narratological Approach

A text is a device conceived in order to produce its Model Reader. I repeat that this reader is not the one who makes the 'only right' conjecture. A text can foresee a Model Reader entitled to try infinite conjectures. The empirical reader is only an actor who makes conjectures about the kind of Model Reader postulated by the text. Since the intention of the text is basically to produce a Model Reader able to make conjectures about it, the initiative of the Model Reader consists in figuring out a Model Author that is not the empirical one and that, at the end, coincides with the intention of the text. (Eco)¹

In considering the tone of Ovid's *Metamorphoses*, scholars most commonly see it as mixed: 'some parts will prove pathetic, some grotesque, some stark, some comic—in fact, a great deal of the essential variety of tone will result automatically'. Wilkinson sees the strands as discrete—comic sections or tragic sections, for example. An extreme example of this sectioning is Albrecht's article which outlines books and their parts according to whether they are serious or comic in tone.² Others, however, see Ovid's tone as equally variable, but view the strands themselves as mixed: 'Abrupt change from epic seriousness to irreverent humour in the same passage is typical of the *Metamorphoses*'.³ Discrepant interpretations of stories, such as those of Actaeon, Pentheus, Perseus, Niobe, Cephalus and Procris, Philemon and Baucis, Pygmalion, Orpheus, Alcyone and Ceyx, Hecuba, often turn on whether the scholar sees the story's tone as serious, comic, or mixed. Though Ovid's comic tone, irreverent or otherwise, has long been recognised as central to understanding the work, there is seldom agreement on what is comic and what is not. Scholarship is also split on the conclusion to be drawn about the function of humour in the work: some see it as superficial and inhumane; others see it as the opposite.⁴ A prime example of these discre-

¹ Umberto Eco, 'Intentio Lectoris: The State of the Art' in *The Limits of Interpretation* (Bloomington and Indianapolis 1990), 58-9.

² L.P. Wilkinson, *Ovid Recalled* (Cambridge 1955) 159; M. von Albrecht, 'Ovids Humor ein Schlüssel zur Interpretation Der Metamorphosen', *Der altsprachliche Unterricht* 6 (1963) 47-72. For this tendency see also B. Otis, *Ovid as an Epic Poet* (Cambridge 1970 2nd ed.) *passim* and R. Humphries, *Ovid Metamorphoses*, (Bloomington 1955) viii.

³ G. Tissol, *The Face of Nature* (Princeton 1997) 96. Cf. O.S. Due, *Changing Forms: Studies in the Metamorphoses of Ovid* (Copenhagen 1974) 144-9; D. Hopkins, 'Dryden and Ovid's "Wit out of Season"', in *Ovid Renewed* ed. Martindale (Cambridge 1988) 189-90; J.B. Solodow, *The World of Ovid's Metamorphoses* (Chapel Hill 1988) 118-19. G.K. Galinsky, *Ovid's Metamorphoses* (Berkeley 1975) 148, though he argues for a mixed tone, denies the Hecuba and Niobe passages any humour.

⁴ The current tendency is to find his humour deep and humane, but for different reasons: Albrecht, 'Ovids Humor' (n.2); W.S. Anderson *Ovid's Metamorphoses, Books 1-5* (Nor-

pancies is the Procne, Philomela, and Tereus tale, provoking among Ovid scholars, perhaps, the most vehement disagreement. Ahl calls the tale one of 'unrelieved horror', which does not 'allow us to escape with a laugh.'⁵ In agreement with him are Curran, Jacobsen, and Pavlock, who see it as a tragedy of brutality and vengeance that displays man's cruelty to man.⁶ Though he does note a few comical elements in the passage, Anderson, perhaps most responsible for recent scholarship on Ovid's use of irreverent humour, mostly sees poignancy and irony—Vergilian and tragic—at work.⁷ For these scholars Ovid's story is deep and humane. Coming to the opposite conclusion, Galinsky finds humour in the tale, charging Ovid with 'cruelty and a loving depiction even of the smallest sadistic detail.'⁸ Richlin deplores in the story the mix 'of clever style with gruesome subject matter', and views the work as an exemplar of what is wrong with art.⁹ Though he does not mention humour, Humphries cites this story—as well as that of Perseus and the Centaurs—as violent and ugly, reflective of a sadistic streak in Ovid.¹⁰ For these scholars the mixture of violence and humour, or simply the violence of the tale, mars Ovid and his work. Up to this point, then, scholarship has argued that the tale is tragic and therefore deep (Ahl, Curran, Jacobsen, Pavlock, Anderson) or wrongly comic and therefore sadistic (Galinsky, Richlin) or excessively violent and therefore sadistic (Humphries). This paper argues against these three views, suggesting that the tone is mixed and that the mixed tone, rather than reflective of sadism in Ovid or his work, offers the reader a seriocomic viewpoint of a world that is many things at once: pathetic and bathetic; cruel and kind; wonderful and horrid.

Although discrepant interpretations are to be expected in any discipline, one may wonder how the same passage can be viewed so very differently. In answer I suggest the reason is that in the tale Ovid frequently uses black humour.¹¹ A black comic tone is a mixed one. It results when an artist

man, Okla. 1997) and *Ovid's Metamorphoses, Books 6-10* (Norman, Okla. 1972); E. Doblhofer, 'Ovidius Urbanus. Eine Studie zum Humor in Ovids Metamorphosen', *Philologus* 104 (1960) 63-91, 223-35; Due, *Changing Forms* (n.3); Hopkins, 'Dryden and Ovid' (n.3); K.S. Meyers, *Ovid's Causes: Cosmogony and Aetiology in the Metamorphoses* (Ann Arbor 1994); Tissot, *The Face of Nature* (n.3); or to find it cruel and misogynistic: Galinsky, *Metamorphoses* (n.3); A. Richlin, 'Reading Ovid's Rapes', in *Pornography and Representation in Greece and Rome*, ed. Amy Richlin, (New York: 1992) 138-79.

⁵ F. Ahl, *Metamorphoses* (Ithaca 1985) 201-2.

⁶ L.C. Curran, 'Rape and Rape Victims in the Metamorphoses', *Arahusa* 11 (1978) 219 and 237; G.A. Jacobsen, 'Apollo and Tereus: Parallel Motifs in Ovid's Metamorphoses', *CJ* 80 (1984) 52; B. Pavlock, 'The Tyrant and Boundary Violation in Ovid's Tereus Episode', *Helios* 18 (1991) 38.

⁷ Anderson, *Metamorphoses* (n.4) 205-37.

⁸ Galinsky, *Metamorphoses* (n.3) 129.

⁹ Richlin, 'Reading Ovid's Rapes' (n.4) 164.

¹⁰ Humphries, *Metamorphoses* (n.2) viii.

¹¹ For a consideration of black humour in the *Metamorphoses*, see P. Peek, 'Black Humor in Ovid's Metamorphoses', *Ramus* 30.2 (2001) 128-51.

interjects comedy into 'material that resists comic treatment'.¹² Black humour may include the humorous treatment of what is grotesque, morbid, terrifying, macabre, sick, pornographic, scatological, ironic, satirical, absurd; and may include detachment, irony, a mocking, apocalyptic tone, parodic undercutting of all systems, one-dimensional characters, wasteland settings, disjunctive structure, self-conscious delight in artistry—a refusal to treat what one might regard as tragic materials tragically. It is the enemy of melodrama and sentimentality.¹³ It exists *in extremis*: 'To the black humorists, however, the real mirth begins when the youth continues to wriggle on the ground with a leg, or more preferably with both legs broken'.¹⁴ Determining any tone is difficult, and is made especially so when, for example, a sentence's literal sense, in the case of sarcasm, is at odds with its intended meaning.¹⁵ One establishes the incongruity (literal sense vs. intent) and enables one to understand the sentence correctly. Black humour is created through a similar incongruity—the comic treatment of uncomic material—the tonal effect of which is destabilising.¹⁶ Since humour may be obscured by the serious subject matter of death or rape, a black comic tone may be easily missed, which accounts, I think, for why scholars' interpretations of this passage are so at odds. Given the difficulty of establishing any tone and the ambiguity inherent in a black comic one, it seems that making a claim for a seriocomic tone is doubly difficult. Consequently a narratological approach to this story has its advantages.

Narratology's focus on the presentation of a story makes it readily applicable to all narratives. Consequently it has been applied successfully to a growing number of Latin and Greek texts.¹⁷ Scholars tend to find in a given narratological model specific aspects that they see as appropriate for, and congenial to, textual exegesis; they have applied these select aspects of narratology to great reward. Nonetheless, since Ovid's *Metamorphoses* offers us complicated narrative levels, multiple points of view, and a variable tone, exegesis of the Procne, Philomela, Tereus story is perhaps more amenable to application of a comprehensive model. De Jong's articulate and fruitful work on the *Iliad* is the sole example of a comprehensive application of a narratological model to an ancient text.¹⁸ In it she exploits the existing theory of Bal's refinement of Genette's model to the full in order to determine its

¹² P. O'Neill, 'The Comedy of Entropy: The Contexts of Black Humour', in Alan R. Pratt (ed.), *Black Humor. Critical Essays* (New York 1993) 74.

¹³ A. Pratt, 'Introduction: The Nature of Black Humor—Defining Black Humor', in Pratt, *Black Humor* (n.12), and O'Neill, 'The Comedy of Entropy' (n.12).

¹⁴ K. Numasawa, 'Black Humor: An American Aspect' in Pratt, *Black Humor* (n.12) 44.

¹⁵ U. Eco, 'Intentional Lectoris: The State of the Art' in *The Limits of Interpretation* (Bloomington and Indianapolis 1990).

¹⁶ O'Neill, 'The Comedy of Entropy' (n.12) 71-2.

¹⁷ For bibliography on narratological approaches to Ovid, see S. Wheeler, *A Discourse of Wonders: Audience and Performance in Ovid's Metamorphoses* (Philadelphia 1999) and *Narrative Dynamics in Ovid's Metamorphoses* (Tübingen 2000).

¹⁸ Irene J.F. de Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers. The presentation of the story in the Iliad* (Amsterdam 1987).

worth through practical application.¹⁹ Just as de Jong's work successfully shows that narratology is capable of displaying the complexity of a text reputed simple, so it is expected that the model she applies will be capable of displaying the complexities of a text reputed complex. For these reasons the model de Jong uses is the one used in this study.²⁰

Whatever model is used, narratology holds two main interpretive advantages. One is that it focuses on the interaction between model author and model reader, thereby providing readers with clues for interpreting the text and determining its tone.²¹ In doing these two things, narratology is concerned with 'the presentation and reception of the story inside the text,' which actual readers uncover by noting the interaction between model author and reader.²² Signs of this interaction include second person addresses of the model reader,²³ negatives that correct the reader's expectations,²⁴ an anonymous focaliser with whom the reader is invited to identify,²⁵ if not situations that suggest what might have been,²⁶ prolepses and analepses that influence the model reader in a number of ways,²⁷ motivation and presupposition that offer the model author's view of things to the model reader.²⁸ Awareness of these interactions enables the reader to see how the model author manipulates the reactions of his model reader. A second advantage is narratology's refinement of point of view, which it calls focalisation. Focalisation is of central importance to the narratological model and it too concerns the interaction between model author and reader—the perceptual, emotional and intellectual presentation of the *fabula*.²⁹ The model author may narrate and focalise the story (N1F1); he may narrate the story but hand over focalisation to

19 De Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) xi.

20 Not all parts of the model are applicable to the Procne, Philomela, and Tereus passage, but many are.

21 For signs of the narrator (model author), of the narratee (model reader), and of their interaction, see M. Bal, *Narratology. Introduction to the Theory of Narrative* trans. C. van Boheemen (Toronto, Buffalo, London 1985) Chapters 2 and 4; and de Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) 41-99.

22 De Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) 36.

23 'You could forgive Medea for loving Jason', 7.85.

24 'Hymen did not bring hallowed words, a happy face, or favorable omen', 10.4-5.

25 'Who would believe if not for the testimony of tradition?', 1.400.

26 'Andromeda would have covered her blushing face with her hands if she had not been bound', 4.682-3.

27 Prolepses are references to events that have yet to occur; analepses are references to events that have already occurred. In each case events may be internal—within the time span of the *fabula* (events of the story proper)—or external—outside the time frame of the *fabula*. For examples of possible influences on the model reader, see de Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) 91.

28 Explanations for why things occur that answer implicit questions for the reader: 'He fought with his tongue because his age kept him from battle', 5.101-2. Explanatory also are similes; permanent facts; general truths. De Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) 41-99.

29 G. Genette, *Narrative Discourse* trans. J. Lewin (Ithaca, New York 1980) 189 and 206 coins the term. But I follow de Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) 31-40 in following Bal's model, *Narratology* (n.21) 100-18.

another character (N1F2); he may hand over narration and focalisation to a secondary character (N2F2).

Determining who is focalising influences how we interpret. One of the examples de Jong offers from the *Iliad* (7.311-12) is an apt illustration of this influence:

- (1) *Αἶαντ' ἀδθ' ἐτέρωθεν εὐκνήμιδες Ἀχαιοὶ
εἰς Ἀγαμέμνονα δῖον ἄγον, κεχαρηότα νίκη.*

Well-greaved Achaians on the other side led, to worthy
Agamemnon, Ajax, happy on account of his victory.

She notes that commentators have tried to explain why Ajax is victorious when heralds ended the duel before either Hector or Ajax had won. She suggests that *κεχαρηότα νίκη* 'represents the focalisation of Ajax, who rejoices about what he interprets as a victory (pp. 101-2)'. Focalisation enables the model author to interact with his model reader in a subtle way: he creates conflict with his narration, which the model reader is left to resolve on his own, giving him a glimpse into Ajax's temperament.

In an effort to determine what belongs to the model author and what to his characters, narratology distinguishes between three types of text: simple narrator-text; character-text; and complex narrator-text. In simple narrator-text the model author narrates and focalises (N1F1) the story. Character-text is speeches. Although the model author and ultimately, the historical one, determines what and how much is said, a character narrates and focalises (N2F2): his identity, status, personality, emotions, audience, situation, and the effect he wishes his words to have influence what he says.³⁰ We interpret accordingly. Complex narrator-text (embedded or secondary focalisation) is when the model author embeds the description of the content of a character's perceptions, thoughts, memory, emotion, feelings.³¹ The author narrates but the character focalises (N1F2). The most straightforward example of embedded focalisation is indirect speech.³² I offer two examples, the first is one of de Jong's from the *Iliad* (15.422-3), the second is one of mine from the *Metamorphoses* (6.449-50):

- (2) *Ἐκταρ δ' ὡς ἐνόησεν ἀνεψίων ὀφθαλμοῖσιν
ἐν κονίησι πεσόντα νεὸς προσάρουθε μελαίνης*

When Hector caught with his eye his nephew fallen
in the dust before the black ship.

- (3) *coeperat, adventus causam, mandata referre
coniugis et celeres missae spondere recursus.*

30 Bal, *Narratology* (n.21) 100; De Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) 226. For this reason no examples in this paper are taken from stories told by a narrator other than Ovid.

31 Bal, *Narratology* (n.21) 111-12; De Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) 38-9.

32 Bal, *Narratology* (n.21) 139-42, does not analyze indirect speech as embedded focalisation; de Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) 114-18, does and, in my opinion, is correct to do so.

[Tereus] began to tell the reason for his coming, his wife's requests, and to promise Philomela's swift return.

In de Jong's example, ἀνεψιὸν ὀφθαλμοῖσιν indicates that the model author presents what Hector, F2, saw. The author narrates but Hector focalises the story for us: he influences the choice of ἀνεψιόν, which stresses the kinship relation of the two.³³ Narrating the event through Hector's focalisation affects tone, enabling the author to increase pathos for the death. Likewise, in my example, *cooperat referre* tells us that Tereus is focalising. At this point in the narrative, Tereus is performing his wife's wishes. *coniugis mandata* helps establish the tenor of his words to Pandion as disinterested—he is serving as messenger for his wife. In the very next moment, his involvement abruptly changes: his wife's wishes become his obsession.

The above two examples illustrate the importance of determining who is focalising. To make this point clearer I offer two additional examples from de Jong (*Iliad* 22.403–4, 11.601) and one from Ovid (6.473–4):

(4) τότε δὲ Ζεὺς δουμιενέεσσι
δῶκεν δεικίσασθαι ἔη ἐν πατρίδῳ γαίῃ.

Then Zeus granted his [Hector's] enemies to dishonor him in his own land.

In general the model author does not speak of enemies and so δουμιενέεσσι is attributable to how Hector views the Greeks not how the model author does.³⁴

(5) εἰσρόπων πόνον αἶπὺν ἰῶκά τε δακρυόεσσαυ

[Achilles] looking upon the rough toil and woeful rout.

αἶπὺν in its figurative sense of 'difficult', 'hard' is found only in embedded focalisation or direct speech. Thus it is likely that F2, Achilles, influences the choice of αἶπὺν.³⁵ Since the rest of the narrative makes it clear that the model author would agree with F2's focalisation, it should be emphasised that F2 influences the model author's word choice but expresses a sentiment that he would probably agree with.³⁶ And so Achilles and the model author's view of things correspond, reinforcing the pathetic tone.

(6) ipso sceleris molimine Tereus
creditur esse pius laudemque a crimine sumit

By the very effort of evil Tereus is believed dutiful and takes praise from his crime.

pius and *laudem* are focalised by Pandion and Philomela; *sceleris* by the model author, who sees Tereus' importuning for what it is. The focalisations,

³³ De Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) 103.

³⁴ De Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) 144.

³⁵ De Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) 142.

³⁶ For double or ambiguous focalisation see Bal, *Narratology* (n.21) 113–14 and de Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) 255 n.11.

instead of reinforcing, contradict one another, creating an ironic tone, further discussion of which is offered below. In each of these three examples of complex narrator-text we see how the narration of the model author becomes focalised for a time by a character and how focalisation influences interpretation of the text and its tone.

Although it was stated above that the model author narrates and focalises simple narrator-text, that a character narrates and focalises character-text, and that the author narrates but a character focalises complex-narrator text, there can be influence in each direction: the model author may influence character-text or embedded focalisation by intruding his own focalisation; F2 may influence simple narrator-text. Ultimately the model author, and the historical author, of course, is the one narrating and focalising everything. By interacting with the model reader (NeFe) in these three types of texts, the model author establishes tone and influences him—and thereby us—to interpret events in a certain way. As already noted this paper examines how the model author creates a mixed black comic tone in the Procne, Philomela, Tereus passage and suggests that he does so in order to depict a world that is many opposite things at once. For the sake of readability, in the following analysis 'Ovid' will be used instead of 'N1F1' or 'model author'; 'we' will be used instead of 'NeFe' or 'model reader'; 'secondary focaliser' instead of 'F2'.

As most readers will know, Pandion was king of Athens. He marries his daughter Procne off to Tereus, the Thracian king, because Tereus helped him defeat his enemies. Missing her sister, Procne asks Tereus to go to Athens and to bring Philomela back to Thrace for a visit. Tereus complies; but when he sees her, he is overcome by lust. Returning to Thrace with Philomela, Tereus locks her in a hut in the woods instead of taking her to Procne. There he repeatedly rapes her and cuts out her tongue so that she cannot divulge the assault. Philomela weaves a tapestry that tells of her rape and dismemberment. An old woman takes the tapestry to Procne, who then rescues her sister. The sisters exact revenge on Tereus by killing Irys, his son by Procne, and feeding his body to him for dinner. Tereus, Procne, and Philomela are metamorphosed into three different kinds of birds.

In telling this tale, Ovid consistently blends the serious and the comic—much of it black. As mentioned above, black humor, in the most general terms, is defined as 'the comic treatment of material which resists comic treatment'. Black humor has a number of characteristics. Irony and the grotesque are two of them, becoming black when taken to extremes.³⁷ They are two main ways that Ovid comically treats these serious events. Ovid creates irony in a number of ways. In this passage he frequently does so by offering comments that are at odds with his character's view of things.³⁸ In example 5

³⁷ 'Satire and irony cross the line dividing self-confident humour from black humour only in *extremis*' O'Neill, 'The Comedy of Entropy' (n.12) 79.

³⁸ This is a prevalent strategy of Ovid. Additional characters he opposes include Apollo, Daphne, Phaethon, Jupiter, Europa, Cadmus, Diana, Actaeon, Narcissus, Penitheus, daughters of Minyas, Perseus, Andromeda, Niobe, Medea, Jason, Scylla, Hercules, Ophelus, Cyparissus, Ceyx, Alcyone, Achilles, and Hecuba.

above we saw how *αἰτῶν* reflects Achilles and Homer's way of looking at things. The two reinforce each other, creating a stable and tragic view. Ovid's view of things is often at odds with his characters',³⁹ creating a destabilised, detached, and ironical viewpoint, the exaggeration of which creates a black comic tone. For example, at the start of story, after introducing us to Tereus and his new bride Procne, Ovid, through omens, tells us that the marriage and the conception of Irys are doomed: pronubial Juno, Hymen, Grace are absent; furies and an owl of ill-omen are present. Characters could only possibly know about the presence of the owl, whose significance they fail to appreciate even if they note its presence. The absence of the first three is a non-event, in narratological terms, not part of the *fabula*. As mentioned above, non-events typically correct readers' expectations.⁴⁰ In this case, we would expect Juno, Hymen, and Grace's presence at a wedding. Their absence is significant. The presence of the furies and owl is an event, part of the story; its narration makes sure that we know nothing good will come of the marriage and birth. In these lines Ovid creates irony⁴¹—taking pains to show, as extremely as possible, the ignorant happiness of his characters,⁴² while ensuring our knowledge of their doom. This introduction to the events culminates in an Ovidian general truth: *usque adeo latet utilitas!* ('To such an extent our advantage escapes us!'). The lines preceding it (434-8) are worth attention:

(7) *gratata est scilicet illis
Thracia, disque ipsis grates egere; diemque,*

39 He is often also at odds with his reader's. One example of this has been noted by S. Mack, *Ovid* (New Haven and London 1988) 117: 'Elsewhere Ovid comically pits reader against narrator, giving us with avuncular condescension the information he seems to think we need. "Don't run away from me," says Jupiter to Io (1.597), in a speech which Ovid soberly interrupts for our benefit: ("for she was running away")'. Additional examples include 2.214; 2.283; 2.330-32; 2.399-400; 3.225; 3.244-8; 3.447; 5.207-8; 6.263; 9.454; 13.561-4.

40 De Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) 61-8. *Liotes* would be an exception: it is not a non-event but an assertion made stronger through negation.

41 Additional examples of Ovid's presentation through negation so as to create irony: 1.452-3 (Apollo's ignorance of Cupid's power); 2.857 (Europa's ignorance of the bull's threat); 3.701 (Pentheus' ignorance of Dionysus' power); 4.683 (Andromeda's absurd actions in light of the danger she is in); 5.80-83 (Eurystus' black comic death by mixing bowl instead of sword); 7.144-6 (The absurdity of Medea's concern for reputation in a minor affair in contrast with her utter disregard for it when committing dreadful wrongs); 8.196 (Icarus' not knowing that the feathers he gleefully handles will cause his death); 9.116-17 (Hercules does not seek to cross the river as quickly as possible but is intent on another exploit when he should realise the danger Nessus poses to his wife and sense the fear she has of him); 10.4-5 (Hymen's presence at Orpheus' wedding being not of good omen but of bad); 11.15-19 (Orpheus' magical singing would have protected him had not the women of the Cicones drowned it out); 12.115 (Achilles throws the spear at Menoetes as if he does not trust his own prowess); 13.393-5 (no hand drives the spear from the body of Ajax; blood does); 14.657-60 (Vertumnus disguised as an old woman kisses Pomona as no old woman would have); 15.779-802 (Romans' failure to pay numerous ill-omens any regard).

42 Pentheus is an extreme example of this, seeking tenderness from relations who respond by tearing him limb from limb. Additional examples are Inachus, Europa, Phaethon, Callisto, Actaeon, Semele, Narcissus, Niobe's children, Pelias' daughters, Daedalus, Icarus, Hercules, Alcione, Achilles, Polymestor, Scylla.

*quaque data est claro Pandione nata tyranno
quaque erat ortus Irys, festum iussere vocari:
usque adeo latet utilitas!*

Thrace naturally congratulates them; they thank the very gods. And the day on which the daughter of Pandion was given to the famous tyrant and on which Irys had been born they bade be called a holiday. To such an extent our advantage escapes us.

But for *scilicet*, the first four lines represent the focalised thought of Thrace and the new parents. They form part of the events of the *fabula*. *scilicet* and *usque adeo latet utilitas* do not.⁴³ They are Ovid's after-the-fact commentary, highlighting for us the irony of his characters' happiness. They are what take the irony to the extreme and what is absent, for example, in the *Iliad* when Homer has Andromache readying Hector's bath in ignorance of his death. Ovid does much the same in the following three examples (471-4, 476-7, 484-5):

(8) [Tereus urges Pandion and Philomela]
*addidit et lacrimas, tamquam mandasset et illas.
pro superi, quantum mortalia pectora caecae
nocitis habent! ipso sceleris molimine Tereus
creditur esse pius laudemque a crimine sumit.*

He even added tears as if she had ordered these too. By the gods, what abundance of sightless darkness mortal hearts possess. By the very effort of crime Tereus is thought pious and takes praise from wickedness.

(9) [Philomela urges Pandion]
*ut eat visura sororem
perque suam contraque suam petit ipsa salutem.*

43 On non-narrative comments, see Bal, *Narratology* (n.21) 126-9. Additional non-narrative comments that create irony: 1.400 (Ovid ironically asserts belief in rocks becoming men because tradition vouches for it); 2.170 (Phaethon would not be able to control the steeds even if he did know how to handle a chariot); 3.138-42 (Actaeon's death is the result of chance not wrong); 4.543-8 (Theban women decide to commit suicide, not thinking that Iro's death is doubtful); 5.2-4 (sounds in the hall of Cepheus are not wedding songs but an uproar presaging battle); 7.84-5 (Jason chances to be more beautiful than usual and so rekindles in Medea the love that she had nearly suppressed. For this reason we could pardon her for loving him); 8.24 (Scylla comes to know Nisus better than she should); 9.456 (Byblis loves her brother not as a brother or sister should); 10.1-3 (Hymen's coming to Orpheus' wedding is in vain); 11.579 (Alcione prays for the return of Ceyx who is already dead); 12.75-7 (Seeking Hector or Cycnus, Achilles fights with Cycnus because Hector's death had been postponed until the tenth year); 13.430-34 (Priam's sending Polydorus to Polymestor would have been wise had he not also sent treasure); 14.25-8 (Circe refuses to help Glaucus, because no one is more susceptible to passion than she); 15.779 (Venus' complaints about the upcoming murder of Julius Caesar are spoken in vain).

that she go to see her sister for (and against) her health's sake she asks.

- (10) [Philomela, having convinced Pandion to let her visit Procne]
et successisse duabus
 id putat infelix, quod erit lugubre duabus
 and doomed she thinks it a success for both what will
 be mourning for both.

Italicised words represent Ovid's commentary that belongs to his interpretation of the story but not to the events of the *fabula* itself. The two, of course, combine to form Ovid's story. The distinction is important: a different created narrator would not tell the story in exactly the same way. With this commentary he influences us to take a particular view of things. In the first we are presented with a world in which human error and irony reign supreme. In the second Ovid gives Philomela's words to her father in indirect speech. Her actual words were probably: *eam visura sororem per meam salutem*. Ovid intrudes his own commentary *contraque suam* into Philomela's to emphasise, yet again, human error and irony. Finally, in 484-5, Ovid intrudes on Philomela's indirect speech, *quod erit lugubre duabus*, so as to influence us in the same way. Two more examples effect the same things.⁴⁴

- (11) [Procne deceived by Tereus]
falsisque piacula manibus infert
 et luget non sic lugendae fata sororis.
 she brings offerings to a non-existent ghost and she
 mourns the fate of a sister not in this way to be
 mourned.

- (12) [When Itys comes in to hug his mother, Procne has the following reaction]
triste parat facinus tacitaque exaestuat ira.
 ut tamen accessit natus matrique salutem
 attulit . . .
 she readies the sad deed and seethes with silent wrath.
 But when even still her son approaches and greets his
 mother . . .

In the first, *non sic lugendae* continues Ovid's theme of human ignorance and irony. In the second *triste facinus* informs us of Procne's intent and creates irony: our knowledge of what will happen versus Itys' ignorance. *tamen* underscores this ignorance, looking forward to *iam sua fata videntem* ('now seeing his fate'), fourteen lines later, when Itys comes to know.⁴⁵ By editorialising Ovid creates ironic tension between his characters' ignorance

⁴⁴ 569-70, 623-5; other examples: 6.565-6; 580; 647-8.

⁴⁵ It should be noted that in examples 7-12 Ovid's irony also serves to create dramatic tension: Ovid never fails to keep the narrative moving.

and our knowledge. This detached view, at odds with his characters', creates the extreme type of irony characteristic of black humor.

Ovidian irony can become even more extreme than that seen in the examples above. In the next two examples we see instances where the irony is even more exaggerated—even more at odds with the characters' view. In the climactic scene (650-52), Tereus' ignorance and ironical existence are the focus:

- (13) *ipse sedens solio Tereus sublimis avito*
vescitur inque suam sua viscera congerit alvum,
tantaque nox animi est: 'Ityn huc accersite' dixit.

He, Tereus, sitting high on his ancestral throne eats and piles into his belly his own innards, and so great is the darkness of his mind: 'Bring Itys in here,' he said.

tantaque nox animi est functions like Ovid's similar expressions in (7) and (8) above. *sublimis* may belong to the events of the *fabula* because it locates Tereus physically. It may also represent Ovid's commentary on events, displaying irony and ignorance for us again: at the moment of greatest horror, Tereus sits happily munching a way. And so *sublimis* appears to serve a dual function.⁴⁶ There is a third possible function: that it is secondarily focalised by Tereus, representing his unspoken happy thoughts. If it does, it is an instance of a secondary focaliser's influence on simple narrator-text. Whatever function applies, irony and dramatic tension are created: we wait expectantly for him to find out the truth. Meanwhile, the double entendre, '*Ityn huc accersite*' ('Bring Itys in here'), is so ironical it is absurd. The next example is equally extreme.

As we have already seen, because of the ominous start to the tale, we know that tragedy will soon occur and involve Procne, Tereus, and Itys in some way. We also know that Pandion is ignorant of the nature of the man he has chosen for his daughter's bedmate. We are not, in part because Ovid expends six verses to explain Tereus' emotional state to us.⁴⁷ An additional six further establish for us the extremity of his passion, giving us Tereus' contemplating the lengths he would go to possess Philomela.⁴⁸ Even so we

⁴⁶ On double or ambiguous focalisation see note 36.

⁴⁷ non secus exarsit conspecta virgine Tereus,
 quam si quis canis ignem supponat aristas
 aut frondem positasque cretmet faenilibus herbas.
 digna quidem facies; sed et hunc innata libido
 exstimulat, pronunqat genus regionibus illis
 in Venerem est: flagrat vitio genisque suoque.

⁴⁸ Having spied the maiden Tereus caught flame no differently than if one should put fire to old husks or bum leaves and hay stored in lofts. In fact her face is worth it; but also inborn lust fueled him as well as being of a people from that area inclined to love: he blazes with the sin of clan and self.' (455-60)

⁴⁸ *inpetus est illi comitum corrumpere curam*
nutricisque fidem nec non ingentibus ipsam
sollicitare datis totumque impendere regnum,
aut rapere et saevo rapiam defendere bello.
et nihil est, quod non effreno captus amore

may still be surprised by the thoughts that run through Tereus' mind when he sees Philomela hug her father: *quotiens amplectitur illa parentem, / esse parens vellet: neque enim minus inpius esset* ('as many times as she hugs her parent he would wish to be parent for he would be no less impious', 481-2). (The omitted ablative of comparison appears to be *Pandione*.) The lines are secondarily focalised: Tereus' idea of *pious*, *inpius*, and *parens* is perversely ironical.⁴⁹ Because of our knowledge of Tereus' thoughts, we are influenced to view Pandion's later speech (496-503) as a reflection of his ignorance and ironical existence:

(14) hanc ego, care gener, quoniam pia causa coegit,
ut volvere ambae, voluisti tu quoque, Tereu,
do tibi perque fidem cognataque pectora supplex,
per superos oro, patrio ut tuearis amore
et mihi sollicito lenimen dulce senectae
quam primum (ormis erit nobis mora longa) remittas!
tu quoque quam primum (satis est procul esse sororem),
si pietas ulla est, ad me, Philomela, redito!

'Dear son-in-law, her, because a pious cause compels,
since both desire, and you desire too, Tereus, I give to
you and by faith and kindred breasts, I, as suppliant, by
the gods, ask that you guard her with a father's love and
the sweet comfort of my troubled years, as soon as
possible (every delay I will see as long) return! You,
too, as soon as possible (it is enough that your sister is
afar) if there is any piety, to me, Philomela, come back!'

Pandion begs Tereus to guard Philomela with a father's love, stressing piety, faith, and kinship. We know Tereus' sense of piety and what type of father he would be; for this reason we cannot but help seeing irony and error in the speech. And so Pandion's echo of Tereus' depraved thought is, I think, a grim wink to us on Ovid's part.

So far we have seen examples of an extreme type of irony created mainly because of an exaggerated incongruity between a character's ignorance of his fate and the knowledge Ovid takes pains to give us. Another typical way Ovid creates exaggerated irony is by having his characters speak or think unnatural things.⁵⁰ For example, Dryden notes the incongruous (or ironical) way Ovid

ausit, nec capiunt inclusas pectora flammās.

'His impulse is to corrupt her attendants' charge and nurse's trust and with no small gifts to tempt her and to expend his entire realm, or to capture her and to protect his capture in savage war. Indeed there is nothing that overcome by unbridled love, he would not dare, and his chest could not contain the fires within.' (461-6)

See discussion below on Dryden and 'umatural thought.'

Additional instances include: Phaethon: *et iam mallet equos nunquam teigitisse paternos, / iam cognosse genus piget et valuisse rogando, / iam Meropis dici cupiens in fertur,* 2.182-4; Marsyas: *quid me mihi detrahis?*, 6.385; Byblis: *quam bene, Caene, tuo poteram nurus esse parentii! / quam bene, Caene, meo poteris gener esse parentii! / omnia, di facerent, essent communin nobis, / praeter avos: tu me vellem generosior esses,* 9. 488-91 (Wilkinson Ovid Recalled [n.2] 207 views these as conceits). Alcione:

has Narcissus speak: 'Would he think of *inopem me copia fecit* and a dozen more of such expressions, pour'd on the neck of one another, and signifying all the same thing?' Ovid is 'ticking [us] to laugh'.⁵¹ Ovid does likewise near the conclusion of the tale, when Progne and Philomela have their revenge. Tereus sits at the table happily munching away and ironically calls for his son Itys (*Ilyn huc accersite*, 652). Progne delightedly (and ironically) proclaims *initus habes, quem poscis* ('whom you ask for you have within', 655).⁵² Next Philomela throws at him the severed head of his son and Tereus laments that he has become the wretched tomb of his son (*seque vocat bustum miserabile nati*, 665). The thought is not one that most fathers, upon having eaten their sons, would express nor one that Propriety expects from someone having done likewise. In the next example (629-35) we see that Progne's thinking is equally incongruous.

(15) (Progne choosing sister over son)
sed simul ex nimia mentem pietate labare
sensit, ab hoc iterum est ad vultus versa sororis
inque vicem spectans ambos 'cur admovet' inquit
'alter blanditias, rapta silet altera lingua?
quam vocat hic matrem, cur non vocat illa sororem?
cui sis nupta, vide, Pandione nata, marito!
degeneras! scelus est pietas in coniuge Tereo'

But at the same time she sensed her mind wavering from too much piety, she turned from him and again to her sister's face and looking at each in turn says 'why does one speak charmingly; the other is silent, tongue gone. Whom he calls mother, why does she not call sister. See what husband you married, daughter of Pandion! You are sullied! A crime is piety toward your spouse Tereus.'

Explanation of the incongruity of her thoughts will benefit from a brief digression on evaluative and affective words.⁵³ Above it was noted that

nunc absens perii, inactor quoque fluctibus absens: Et sine me, me pontus habet, 11.700-701 (For a discussion of this wordplay, see G.M.H. Murphy, *Ovid's Metamorphoses XI* [Bristol 1979] 77.) The debate between Ajax and Ulysses (13.6-390), good discussions of which can be found in Due, *Changing Forms* (n.3) 153-4 and R. Coleman, 'Structure and Intention in the *Metamorphoses*', *CQ* 21 (1971) 474f. (Coleman and Wilkinson Ovid Recalled [n.2] 230, think Ovid's sympathies lie with Ulysses. I would argue they lie with neither or both.) Hecuba's speech, which Seneca, *Contr.* 9.5.17, marked as distasteful: 13.494-532. Polyxena's speech, 13.460-73, concerning which, Due, *Changing Forms* (n.3) 155, in partial agreement with Otis, *Ovid as an Epic Poet* (n.2) 285, writes the following: 'apparently the taste for such exaggerated heroism displayed in macabre contexts was a fact upon which Ovid could count—and did count.'

⁵¹ I. Dryden, 'Preface to Fables Ancient and Modern, translated into verse', in *John Dryden: Of Dramatic Poesy and Other Critical Essays* ed. G. Watson (London 1962) 279.

⁵² H. Fränkel, *Ovid: A Poet Between Two Worlds* (Berkeley and Los Angeles 1945) 216 n. 42 rightly notes that the double entendre is an instance of grim humor.

⁵³ On evaluative and affective words, see de Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) 136-48. Additional instances of evaluative and affective words include 1.125-131 (various words condemn iniquity of iron age); 2.111 (*magnanimus* evaluates Phaethon); 3.354 (*dira*

determining what belongs to the thought of Ovid and what to his characters' is crucial to the interpretive act. Once one determines what is focalised by Ovid, value words can help determine his view of events. In the *Iliad*, passages focalised by Homer often speak of war as woeful and costly. Recognition of these value words enables us to conclude that Homer—at least in part—viewed war in this way.⁵⁴ Ovid often uses value words of his characters' actions.⁵⁵ The words *sceleris*, *crimine*, *triste*, *facinus* from examples (8) and (12) above are evaluative and affective: they suggest Ovid's censure of the acts and they invite us to do the same.⁵⁶ Overcome by emotion, Tereus and Procne commit these horrific acts and errors of judgment. It is with Tereus in mind that *sed simul ex nimia mentem pietate tabare/ sensit* should be considered: like Tereus', Procne's idea of *pietas* is blackly ironical.⁵⁷ For this mistaken thinking, Ovid had paved the way some lines earlier when he noted that Procne would confuse right and wrong—*fasque nefasque confusura* (585-86). The lines following *sensit* further demonstrate the strangeness of her confusion. Her rationale for murder is unnatural. The swiftness of her hesitation is so abrupt it suggests an undercutting of serious tone and reminds one of Jove's comic deliberation over whether to give Io to Juno at 1.617-21. These three things are exaggerated and calculated to be as

superbia evaluates Narcissus); 4.2 (*temeraria* evaluates Alcithoe); 5.8 (*belti temerarius auctor* evaluates Phineus); 7.300 (*callida* evaluates Medea); 8.85 (*heu facinus* evaluates Scylla); 9.120 (*fallere* evaluates Nessus); 10.56 (*avidus* evaluates Orpheus); 11.14 (*insana Erinyes* evaluates the women of the Cicones); 12.128 (*fremebundus* evaluates Achilles); 13.434 (*avarus* evaluates Polimestor); 14.25-27 evaluates Circe; 15.785 (*nefas* evaluates the conspirators who kill Caesar).

⁵⁴ De Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) 43.

⁵⁵ Evaluative and affective words may also establish the tenor of direct or indirect speech: cum *blamātra* viro Procne 'si gratia' dixit (440)

Procne 'winsomely' speaks. At 476 Philomela will be described as *blanda* when she asks her father, in indirect speech, to let her visit her sister. At 493 the tone of the upcoming speech is indicated by *lacrimis abortis* (tears rising). Cf. 513 *exclamat* (shouts).

⁵⁶ Tereus: he compares him to destructive fire (455-7); calls him *barbarus* and *tyrannus ferus* (515 and 549); emphasises Philomela's virginity and helplessness (*virginem et unam*, 524); expresses disbelief that he assaulted her repeatedly after having cut out her tongue (*vix ausim credere*, 561), referring to her body as *lacerum* (562); describes his return to Procne thus: 'he manages to return to Procne after such deeds': (*sustinet ad Procnem post Italia facta reverti*, 563).

Procne: He refers to her eyes as *hard oculisque inimitibus* (621) and calls her joy cruel: *crudelia gaudia* (653).

Philomela: there is perhaps a hint of condemnation of Philomela when he describes her appearance as she is about to throw Tereus his son's head: *sparsis furiali caede capillis* (657)—'her hair spattered with mad slaughter'; *furiali caede* may imply criticism. Prior to the slaughter of Ilys, Ovid describes Philomela compassionately: as a helpless hare (516-518); a frightened lamb (527); a dove (529); *infelix* (602). Ilys is not criticised.

⁵⁷ The use of similar words to condemn Tereus and Procne is paralleled by Ovid's connecting them in another way. He uses similar words to describe their mental states: (Tereus) *nec capiunt inclusas pectora flammās* ('his heart cannot accommodate the enclosed flame', 466); (Procne) *iram non capit ipsa suam Procne*: ('Procne herself cannot accommodate her own anger', 653).

incongruous as possible;⁵⁸ and they, like the other examples we have seen, jar with the subject matter, creating a mixed serio-comic tone. Ovid's varied use of kinship words also helps create this ironical mixture.

seque vocat bustum miserabile nati, from above, is an instance of indirect speech. As noted previously, indirect speech shows secondary focalisation. All indirect speech is secondarily focalised, but not all that is secondarily focalised is in indirect speech (see example 1 above and examples 21 and 22 below). Determining secondary focalisation that is not in indirect speech can be quite difficult. Helpful are words, like *nati*, that denote kinship ties because they often mark a passage as secondarily focalised.⁵⁹ In example 2 above we saw that Homer used a kinship word in secondary focalisation—*Ἐκτωρ δ' ὡς ἐνόησεν δνεψιόν*—to increase pathos. In Ovid's tale, kinship ties and their dissolution play an integral part of this story. It is no surprise then that the passage is replete with familial words: *coniunx*, *gener*, *genetrix*, *germana*, *maritus*, *mater*, *nata*, *natus*, *nepos*, *parens*, *pater*, *socerus*, *soror*, *vir*—some used unexpectedly and comically; others straightforwardly in contexts of affection and concern. When their use corresponds to the subject matter, like Homer's use of *ἀνεψιόν*, the result is typically a serious, unmixed tone. When the two are at odds, comic irony may result. These first three (504-5, 596-8, 603-5) examples display congruity:

(16) [Pandion urges his daughter to return soon]
mandabat pariterque suae dabat oscula natae,
et lacrimae mites inter mandata cadebant;

he asks and at the same time kisses his daughter and
soft tears fall as he asks.

(17) [Procne rescues Philomela]
venit ad stabula avia tandem
exulataque euhoeque sonat portasque refringit
germanamque rapit

finally she came to the far-off hut and screams and cries
'euhoe' and breaks down the door and takes her sister

⁵⁸ Contrasting this episode with the similar one in Euripides' *Medea* may help one to see more clearly the difference between the suggested black comic tone here and the tragic tone there. For a good part of the play *Medea* wavers in her decision. Her anguish is fully developed and emotionally compelling. Despite her love for the children she says she kills to hurt Jason and to insure that no one from the royal family kills them in retaliation. Her justification, however perverse, is naturally presented. The act of murder is not narrated beyond the screams of the children. Philomela in contrast barely wavers. Her justification is perverse but also unnatural—propriety and epic expect no such reasoning. Finally, the murder itself is not only narrated but overly elaborate: Philomela watches the act; strikes more than the fatal first blow; cuts up and cooks the body—still alive his cut up body parts hiss, moan, and leap—much like the killed oxen in Book 12 of the *Odyssey*.

⁵⁹ Familial words often indicate that a passage is secondarily focalised, de Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) 103. Instances of familial words marking secondary focalisation include 1.483-5; 2.49; 3.3-5; 4.603-6; 5.212; 7.96; 8.145; 9.107; 10.60; 11.384-8; 12.580-83; 13.415-17; 14.61-2; 15.761-4.

- (18) *nacta locum Procne sacrorum pignora demit
oraque develat miseræ pudibunda sororis
amplexumque petit;*

having found a place Procne takes off the ritual garb and unveils the ashamed face of her wretched sister and seeks embrace.

In each example the familial word helps mark the passage as secondarily focalised. The secondary focalisation and the kinship word are congruous, displaying a character's familial love and concern in an expected and serious manner. In the next two examples (647-9, 656-60), kinship words are found in incongruous contexts.

- (19) (Procne about to get her revenge)
*his adhibet coniunx ignarum⁶⁰ Terea mensis
et patrii moris sacrum mentita, quod uni
fas sit adire viro, cornites famulosque removit.*

The wife calls unaware Tereus to this table and having invented an observance of her father's customs, which permits only a husband's presence, she dismissed the attendants and slaves.

- (20) *quaerenti iterumque vocanti,
sicut erat sparsis furiali caede capillis,
prosiluit Ityosque caput Philomela cruentum
misit in ora patris nec tempore maluit ullo
posse loqui et meritis testari gaudia dictis.*

seeking and calling repeatedly just as she was her hair spattered with mad slaughter she leapt out and Philomela sent Itys' bloodied head into his father's face and at no time preferred to be able to speak and to witness her joy in fitting words.

In 19 the choice of *coniunx* is surprising. At a moment when Procne is to feed Tereus their son for dinner, Ovid refers to her with a word that conjures up an image of a woman dutifully getting dinner ready for her husband. But the dinner is an abomination and so we are asked to see *coniunx* as ironical and inappropriate, directed at creating a black tone. *patris* in 20 functions similarly. The focalisation of *patris* by Itys' severed head is ironical and outrageous, introducing black humor. *patris* may also represent Philomela's unspoken words as she tosses Tereus his son's head—'Catch, Dad.' In these examples, irony of a particularly extreme, and therefore black, type is again used.

Though in the above examples secondary focalisation is clearly present, other instances are less certain. In each of the following examples (520-21,

⁶⁰ *ignarum* may be focalised by Procne, Tereus' ignorance being her mind's foremost delight.

581-2), the question, who is focalising—Ovid or the character—is more difficult to determine:

- (21) *cum rex Pandione natam
in stabula alta trahit silvis obscura vetustis*

when the king dragged Pandion's daughter into the high hut hidden in an aged forest.

- (22) (Procne reads the message Philomela sent)
*evolvit vestes saevi matrona tyranni
fortunaequa suae carmen miserabile legit*

matron of the savage tyrant unrolled the cloth and read her fortune's wretched tale

alta and *obscura* help describe for us Philomela's feeling of fear and helplessness as Tereus drags her to the hut. But are we to read the adjectives as focalised by Ovid or by Philomela, reflecting her thoughts?⁶¹ In the second example, the evaluative and affective words *saevi tyranni* and *miserabile* establish what Procne feels as she reads the tapestry. They also may be a reflection of Procne's thoughts, though Ovid would surely agree with both. *matrona* is less clear. Does it represent Procne's reflection on being married to, and having had a child with, a man who has been assaulting her sister for a year—'I matron of this cruel tyrant'? Or does it come from Ovid for thematic reasons? In each instance perhaps double focalisation is at work.⁶² Whether this be the case or not, the tone is congruous, seriously establishing Philomela and Procne's emotional states. In considering the focalisation and tone of the above seven passages, we have seen five have a serious tone and two, a mixed one. This mixed tone is extremely ironical (or incongruous), which is a characteristic of black humor, as is exaggerated grotesquery to which we turn next.

The grotesque, like irony, when taken to the extreme, becomes black.⁶³ Exaggeration of the grotesque creates tension with the serious subject matter. As mentioned earlier, Ovid consistently interjects the comic into the serious. And so as we read we must stand on guard to see when and how Ovid will inject levity. Exaggerated grotesquery is present in many stories Ovid narrates;⁶⁴ it is present in the killing and cooking of Itys. The example I offer, however, Tereus' attack of Procne (555-60), is perhaps the most exaggerated and gruesome example of grotesquery in the stories Ovid narrates:

⁶¹ A later passage, I think, suggests that *alta* and *obscura* are focalised by Philomela: 'venit ad stabula *avia tandem*' (596): 'finally she [Procne] comes to the far-off hut.' *tandem* certainly reflects Procne's anxiousness to find her sister; *stabula* is here modified by *avia* rather than *alta* and *obscura*—the change in modifiers may be due to the change in influence of focalisers.

⁶² For double or ambiguous focalisation, see note 36. For implicit focalisation see de Jong, *Narrators and Focalizers* (n.18) 118-22.

⁶³ See footnote 37.

⁶⁴ Exaggerated grotesquery can also be found in these stories: Phaethon; Heliades; Actaeon; Pentheus; Perseus; Niobe; Hercules; Orpheus; Achilles; Hecuba. See Peek, 'Black Humor' (n.11) 141-5.

rest of the work. The consistent introduction of the comic into the serious creates this distance.⁷² It also helps unify the work, offering us a seriocomic worldview.⁷³ And so the different reactions to the passage, mentioned at paper's start, constitute only part of the ironic result. If we wish to pass verdict on Ovid or his work, we need to consider the narrative as a whole, made up of (but distinct from) its various parts. For this reason it seems that scholars' diverse reactions to this passage are correct but only partially so: each fails to observe the many different reactions Ovid elicits from us.⁷⁴

Bowling Green State University

PHILIP S. PEEK

⁷² For various ways he introduces humor into the stories of Apollo and Daphne; Jupiter and Europa; and Alpheus and Arethusa, see B. E. Stirrup, 'Techniques of Rape: Variety and Wit in Ovid's *Metamorphoses*', *GR* 24 (1977) 170-84.

⁷³ It seems as though a mark of Ovid is the ability to make his work be two (seemingly) mutually exclusive things at the same time. For many examples of this, see Due, *Changing Forms* (n.3) *passim*.

⁷⁴ For their suggestions for improvement, I thank the reader, James Keenan, and James Pfundstein.